

Stability Constants of Some Bivalent Metal Chelates of O-Thymol Aldoxime

S. L. GARG & K. K. PANDAY

Chemical Laboratories, Government Science College, Gwalior (M.P.)

Received 5 January 1972

Stability constants of complexes of some bivalent metals viz., UO_2^{+2} , Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} and Co^{+2} with O-Thymol aldoxime have been determined potentiometrically in 75% dioxane and 0.1M sodium perchlorate medium. The order of stability constants for the complexes conforms to the Basolo and Pearson stability order.

Considerable work has been reported on the determination of stability constants of metal complexes with *o*-hydroxy aldoximes and ketoximes¹. However, similar studies on the metal complexes with *o*-thymol aldoxime have not been reported so far. In view of this, the stability constants of bivalent metal complexes with *o*-thymol aldoxime have been determined potentiometrically.

EXPERIMENTAL

O-Thymol aldoxime was prepared from *o*-thymol aldehyde² (b.p. 130° at 15 mm.).

An Elico pH-meter, LI-10, with a glass electrode of 0-13 pH range, was employed for potentiometric titrations.

The solutions of metal ions were prepared from analytical grade samples of corresponding sulphates or nitrates. All these were standardized complexometrically by EDTA titrations. Dioxane (BDH, A.R.) was freed from peroxide by refluxing it with sodium for 8-10 hrs. and distilling over sodium before use. Sodium perchlorate (BDH) was added to all solutions to keep the ionic strength constant (0.1M). All measurements were made at 30° ± 0.5°.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.2M) solution :

- (i) 2.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.04M) + 2.0 ml $NaClO_4$ (1.0M) + 1.0 ml H_2O + 15 ml dioxane.
- (ii) 2.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.04 M) + 2.0 ml $NaClO_4$ (1.0 M) + 1.0 ml H_2O + 5.0 ml ligand (0.01 M) in dioxane + 10 ml dioxane.
- (iii) 2.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.04 M) + 2.0 ml $NaClO_4$ (1.0 M) + 1.0 ml metal salt (0.005 M) + 5.0 ml ligand (0.01 M) in dioxane + 10.0 ml dioxane.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti³ was applied to find out the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL . In all the cases, correction for change in volume on mixing dioxane and aqueous solutions (Total volume = 19.67 ml due to contraction in volume from 20.0 to 19.67 ml) has been made.

In the ligand, it is the chelated phenolic OH group which takes part in complex formation and the protons are replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, $Y = 1$. (This has been confirmed by titrating mixtures of metals and ligand in the ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 potentiometrically by 0.1 *M* NaOH).

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}H$ values at various pH values were calculated; and a curve between pH and corresponding $\bar{n}H$ values was plotted (Fig. 1). From this curve, the value of practical pK_{OH} was calculated at $\bar{n}H$ values of 0.5.

LIGAND PROTON FORMATION CURVE
OF O-THYMOL ALLOXIME

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexion equilibria (Fig. 2). From these formation curves, the values of stepwise stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ (Table 1) were calculated at $\bar{n}$ values of 0.5

TABLE 1

Stability constants of bivalent metal complexes with o-thymol alloxime

Metal ion	H ⁺	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)	UO ₂ (II)
$\log K_1$	12.20	—	11.45	7.95	10.80
$\log K_2$	—	11.60	8.15	7.15	9.85
$\log \beta_2$	—	23.70*	19.60	15.10	20.65

* The values of $\log \beta_2$ for copper chelate was obtained as the value 'Twice of pL at $\bar{n} = 1.0$ '.

and 1.5 respectively. In case of copper chelate, the formation of 1 : 1 chelate was complete in most acidic solutions. It has been found that $\log K_1 > \log K_2$ in all the cases.

FIG. - 2
FORMATION CURVES OF METAL COMPLEXES
WITH O-THYMOL ALDOXIME.

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates was found to be : $\text{Cu}^{+2} > \text{UO}_2^{+2} > \text{Ni}^{+2} > \text{Co}^{+2}$. This order is in agreement with Basolo and Pearson⁴ with the exception of UO_2^{+2} . But Cu^{+2} forms a more stable complex than UO_2^{+2} with ligands containing one oxygen and one nitrogen as donor atoms⁵. Hence, the order of stability of the chelates determined is justified.

One of the authors (SLG) is grateful to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi for financial assistance.

REFERENCES

1. 'Stability Constants', Special Publication No. 17, Chemical Society, London, 1964.
2. L. M. Liggett and H. Diehl, *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **52**, 191; *Chem. Abs.*, 1947, **41**, 110.
3. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
4. F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, 'Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions', p. 16, John Wiley & Sons., Inc., New York, 1958.
5. R. M. Izatt, W. C. Fernelius and B.P. Block, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1955, **59**, 235.

